

THE DIGITAL SHIFT: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF TECHNOLOGY INTEGRATION IN EDUCATIONAL SETTINGS

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ABSTRACT

Using technology in the classroom has become popular as high-quality education is prioritized for a sustainable future. The objective of the study is to thoroughly review and synthesize the literature on technology integration in educational settings with a focus on the role of educational leadership, challenges faced by teachers, and the evidence-based association between teacher training and the outcomes of technology integration. The researchers follow the method of systematic review. This method entails finding, selecting, and combining recent studies to offer a thorough and trustworthy review of a topic. The research involved empirical evidence from peer-reviewed literature (2015-2025) to evaluate the impact of digital tools on pedagogy, equity, and student performance. Data were gathered from ResearchGate, Education Resource Information Center (ERIC), Google Scholar, and EBSCOhost. The study revealed that when teachers receive the right training, have access to enough digital resources, and have the support of leaders, technology integration works well in the classroom. Moreover, the research shows that to successfully use sustainable technology, it's important to use various methods. This means that resources must be shared equally, leaders must have a clear plan, and there must be continuous support to teachers. Without these important components, the technological integration in the classroom may face different barriers that may hinder its success.

Keywords: *technology integration, educational leadership, digital equity, teachers training, COVID-19*

INTRODUCTION

Application of technology in learning spaces has evolved extensively, altering pedagogic practice, enhancing learner engagement, and addressing typical learning issues. This systematic review synthesizes evidence from the studies that provided data on the benefits and limitations of applying technology in learning spaces in various settings.

Student-centered learning is significantly affected by digital technology. In alignment with previous studies, Wali and Popal argue that technology has revolutionized paradigms in education from teacher-centered to student-centered, increasing participation and improving active learning practices in the classroom (Wali & Popal, 2020). This is echoed by Joshi and Koirala, who observe that access to digital sources and web-based learning platforms hold enormous potential for individualized learning despite access equity and teacher support challenges (Bishnu & Koirala, 2023).

However, effective use of technology in the learning environment is accompanied by an array of challenges. Long-standing issues, as presented by (Aurangzeb et al., 2024) still bedevil the widespread use of technology, with perceived usefulness and usability of these technologies playing important roles that influence the readiness of teachers to adopt them. In addition, the systematic review by (Rasimin et al., 2024), highlights the importance of breaking technology adoption barriers such as poor training for teachers and ongoing inequalities, especially in nations such as Indonesia (Rasimin et al., 2024). Nevertheless, the use of artificial intelligence-based tools, as presented by Familoni and Onyebuchi, further presents a complicated element where, although there may be potential gains of increased student engagement, there are enormous issues of data privacy as well as the exacerbation of education inequalities (Familoni & Onyebuchi, 2024).

In addition, Henderson et al., findings explain students' views on effective digital technologies in higher education as revealing that existing education systems tend to restrict the nature of technology use owing to legacy assessment traditions based on isolated performance (Henderson et al., 2015). Such restriction justifies educational institutions reforming their assessment methods to accommodate newer technology tools and their collaborative potential.

COVID-19 is not only impacting students; it is also affecting teachers and parents globally. UNESCO states that more than 1.5 billion students across 195 countries are unable to go to school due to the closure of schools (UNESCO, 2020b). This virus is creating major disruptions in the education system. It affects exams, grading procedures, and the beginning of new semesters or terms. It may also lead to the prolongation of the ongoing school year. During the COVID-19 pandemic, great emphasis was put on how learning had to be modified because the students and instructors could not engage face-to-face. This included novel ways of learning that ensured safety for all by being able to accommodate social distancing. These new ways also needed to be easy to use and adapt to changing situations. If there was a reliable internet connection, these ways could

be relied upon to function well.

The application of technologies in Philippine learning institutions has ushered in both significant success and ongoing challenges, most notably in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic. The pandemic accelerated the implementation, forcing rapid adaptation to the use of technology in distance learning and altering the manner in which learning institutions utilize technology as a pedagogical tool and means of learning based on the study of (Mastul et al., 2023). However, despite the encouraging potential for effective change, there are ongoing challenges such as digital literacy and infrastructural inefficiencies, as well as a requirement for general teacher training, that are significant barriers to be overcome so that the ultimate potential of said technologies can be achieved (Kilag et al., 2023).

In addition, Technical and Vocational Education (TVE) has been recognized to play a key role in offering students technical skills, which aligns with the expanding demands of the modern labor market fueled by technology (Kilag et al., 2023). Skills development focus finds resonance with increased acceptance of the necessity for curriculum reforms aligning curriculum provision with the demands of the industries, a matter that has been examined by Almerino et al. as well in the evaluation of the Philippine K-12 system (Almerino et al., 2020).

Moreover, educational leadership emerges at this stage of change. Educational leaders are responsible for initiating strategic technology projects aligned with the vision of enhancing educational quality and accessibility (Sarong, 2023). Such direct vision is critical in leading an educational culture that is innovation- and flexibility-oriented, which are the education that are among the collective efforts necessary to better improve the learning experience and employability of Filipino students (Trinidad et al., 2020).

Research Questions

1. What is the role of educational leadership in facilitating the successful use of technology in classrooms and learning areas?
2. What are the challenges teachers face when trying to use technology in their classrooms?
3. What is the evidence based on the association between teacher training, and specific outcomes of technology integration in educational settings?

METHODOLOGY

The researchers performed a systematic review of the literature on technology integration in educational settings. According to Gough et al., (2017), a systematic review is the process of choosing, identifying, and synthesizing previous studies to give a thorough and trustworthy representation of the topic that is being reviewed. It was used as the methodological design to compile the best available research on the predetermined study topics. The aim of this methodology is to have a critical analysis of the findings from

different studies, papers, and reviews. This creative technique guarantees the study's accuracy, methodological soundness, comprehensiveness, and objectivity.

In conducting this review, studies that are aligned with the objectives of this review are considered. The following topics were taken into consideration: leadership, teaching styles, technology integration, K–12 and higher education settings, and classroom technology use from 2015–2025. English peer-reviewed papers, and journals are also taken into account. Excluded materials are opinionated publications, studies that do not focus on educational settings, books, journals, institutional studies, and other sources that are not formally published and peer-reviewed. The study will be using the following academic databases: ResearchGate, Education Resource Information Center (ERIC), Google Scholar, and EBSCOhost.

RESULTS

Table I below shows the research articles included in the systematic literature review.

Table 1. Research Articles used for the Systematic Review

Research No.	Author/s	Research Title	Year of Publication
1	Zhong, L.	The effectiveness of digital leadership at K-12 schools in Mississippi regarding communication and collaboration during CCRS implementation. Dissertation Abstracts International Section A: Humanities and Social Sciences	2016
2	Emmanuel, O.	The Role of Technology in Enhancing Educational Leadership	2025
3	Qasimov, G.	View of Instructional Leadership and Technology Integration in Enhancing Teacher Effectiveness and Student Learning	2025

4	Hafiza Hamzah, N., Khalid M. Nasir, M., & Abdul Wahab, J.	The Effects of Principals' Digital Leadership on Teachers' Digital Teaching during the Covid-19 Pandemic in Malaysia.	2021
5	Gay Cruz Gabitanan, C.	Technology Leadership Techniques and Competencies and the Teaching Effectiveness of the New Millennium. International Journal of Research Publications	2024
6	ANTHONY, M.	Technology Leadership Standards of Education Leaders, Teachers' Technological Adoption and the Integration of Technologies in the Classroom. International Journal of Research Publications	2023
7	Raman ,A. and Thannimalai, R.	Importance of Technology Leadership for Technology Integration: Gender and Professional Development Perspective	2019
8	Norhanida Samsudin, & Muhammad	Teacher Technological Leadership: Realising Potentials and Practices.	2020
9	Kilag, K. T., Magaso, J.N., Brian, K., Carmel, A., Magdalene, A., & Rivamonte, W. D.	Technical Vocational Education in the Philippines for Sustainable Development	2023
10	Sarong, J.	Exploring Transformative Leadership Approaches in Modern Educational Institutions.	2023
11	Sarong, J.	Fostering collaboration and team effectiveness in educational leadership: strategies for building high-performing teams and networks.	2024

12	Yuting, Z., Adams, D., & Lee, K. C. S.	A systematic review of E-leadership and its effects on student learning in higher education.	2022
13	AlAjmi, M. K.	The impact of digital leadership on teachers' technology integration during the COVID-19 pandemic in Kuwait. International Journal of Educational Research	2022
14	Paran, L. R. L., De Leon, J. L., & Pade, E. Q.	Challenges in Technology Integration for Elementary Teachers.	2024
15	Barcelona, K. E. P., Daling, B. A. J., Doria, P., Balangiao, S. J., Mailes, M. J., Chiang, P. M., & Ubatay, D.	Challenges and Opportunities of TLE Teachers in Philippine Public Schools: An Inquiry.	2023
16	DAVIS, I. C.	Extent of Readiness and Challenges of Teachers of the Fast Learners in the Implementation of Education 4.0.	2023
17	Baticulon, R. E., Sy, J. J., Alberto, N. R. I., Baron, M. B. C., Mabulay, R. E. C., Rizada, L. G. T., Tiu, C. J. S., Clarion, C. A., & Reyes, J. C. B.	Barriers to Online Learning in the Time of COVID-19: A National Survey of Medical Students in the Philippines	2021
18	Pelila, J. R. O., Bag-ongan, Q. F. L., Talania, J. L. P., & Wakat, G. S.	Factors and Barriers Influencing Technology Integration in the Classroom	2022
19	Wali, A. Z., & Popal, A. W.	The Emerging Issues and Impacts of Technology in Classroom Learning	2020

20	Vergonia, B., & Mombas, S. E.	Ready to go? Profiling Philippines high school teachers' readiness for blended learning in post-COVID-19 e	2022
21	Indalecio, R.	Western Pacific Teachers' Perceptions of Implementing Technology in the Classroom	2022
22	Jadman, M.-A. P., & Emerald, M.	Teachers' information and communication technology (ict) competencies	2023
23	Bishnu Maya Joshi, & Padma Koirala	Enhancing Economics Education Through Digital Resources and Online Learning	2023
24	Marcial, D. E.	ICT Social and Ethical Competency among Teacher Educators in the Philippines	2017
25	Hamim, H.	Educational Technology Evolvement During The Covid-19 Pandemic	2024
26	Bernardo, A. B. I., Wong-Fernandez, B., Macalagueng Jr, M. D., & Navarro, R. C.	Filipino senior high school teachers' continuing professional development attitudes: Exploring the roles of perceived demand amid a national education reform. Journal of Research, Policy & Practice of Teachers & Teacher Education	2020
27	Shibing, Z.	Enable Technology to Continuously Empower the Professional Development of Teachers	2024
28	Boholano, H. B., Merin, J. A., & Dapat, L. C.	Building online facilitating skills in the new normal	2021
29	Maala, E. B., & Lagos	Technological Leadership of School Heads and Teachers' Technology Integration	2022

30	Caena, F., & Redecker, C	Aligning teacher competence frameworks to 21st century challenges: The case for the European Digital Competence Framework for Educators (Digcompedu)	2019
31	Pietro, D., & Biagi, G.	The likely impact of COVID-19 on education: Reflections based on the existing literature and recent international datasets.	2020
32	Vakaliuk, T. A., Osova, O. O., Chernysh, O. A., & Bashkir, O. I.	Checking Digital Competence Formations of Foreign Language Future Teachers using Game Simulators	2022
33	Almacen, R. M., Castilla, D., Gonzales, G., Gonzales, R., Costan, F., Costan, E., Enriquez, L., Batoon, J., Villarosa, R., Aro, J. L., Evangelista, S. S., Maturan, F., Wenceslao, C., Atibing, N. M., & Ocampo, L.	Preparedness Indicator System for Education 4.0 with FUCOM and Rough Sets. Systems	2023
34	Mastul, A.-R. H., Vera, C. T. de, & Jayme, C. B.	Understanding the Use of EduTech in Schools in the Philippines: Recommendations for Effectiveness	2023
35	Aurangzeb, W., Kashan, S., & Rehman, Z. U.	Investigating Technology Perceptions Among Secondary School Teachers A Systematic Literature Review on Perceived Usefulness and Ease of Use	2024
36	Las.	Development of J48 Algorithm-Based Application in Predicting Teacher's Techno-Pedagogical Competence	2020

37	Eslit, E. R.	Charting the Future of Philippines Education: Navigating the Intersection of K-12 Education, the Fourth Industrial Revolution (IR 4.0), and Internationalization	2023
38	Henderson, M., Selwyn, N., & Aston, R.	What works and why? Student perceptions of “useful” digital technology in university teaching and learning	2015
39	Olid-Luque, M., Ayllón-Salas, P., Arco-Tirado, J. L., & Fernández-Martín, F. D.	Impact of Self-Regulated Learning Programs in Primary Education: A Systematic Review	2024
40	Qureshi, M. I., Khan, N., Raza, H., Imran, A., & Ismail, F.	Digital Technologies in Education 4.0. Does it Enhance the Effectiveness of Learning? A Systematic Literature Review	2021

Educational Leadership and Technology Integration

1. The roles of educational leadership in implementing successful technology integration.

The roles of educational leadership in implementing technology integration into practice successfully. These are the roles of educational leaders in integrating technology into the classroom, as determined by the material reviewed and compiled.

Table 2.

Roles of Educational Leadership on Technology Integration

Roles of Educational Leadership	Research Article
1. Clear Vision	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,10,13,29,34
2. Continuous Professional Development	1,2,3,4,5,7,9,10,13,27,30,32,35,37
3. Ethical Approach	1,2,4,6,24,
4. Digital Citizenship	4,5,6,7,12,13,24,32
5. Community Engagement	4,8,9,10,11

2. Teachers' Challenges in Technological Integration

These are the challenges faced by teachers in integrating technology into the classroom, as determined by the material reviewed and compiled.

Table 3.

The Teachers' Challenges in Technological Integration

Teachers' Challenges in Technological Integration	Research Article
1. Limited Access to Resources	14, 15, 16, 17, 23, 25, 31, 33, 34, 38
2. Resistance to Change	14, 25, 34
3. Lack of Professional Development	14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 22, 25, 35, 36, 37

3. Teachers Training and Professional Development

Table 4.

Teachers Training and Professional Development for Technological Integration

Teachers Training and Professional Development	Research Article
Comprehensive Training Programs	
1. Technical Skills training	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 9, 10, 13, 20, 21, 22, 24, 28, 34, 35, 36, 37, 39, 40
2. Professional Development Workshops	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 9, 10, 13, 26, 27, 28, 37
3. Continuous Support	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 9, 10, 13, 20, 21, 22, 31, 35, 37
4. Integration of ICT in Curriculum	20, 21, 25, 27, 30, 35

DISCUSSION

1. The Roles of Educational Leadership on Implementing Successful Technology Integration.

The various functions that educational leadership plays in a successful technology integration are shown in Table 2. The smooth integration of technology into an educational context is primarily based on excellent educational leadership. School leaders who articulate and promote a unified vision for digital learning create a roadmap that aligns teaching practices and yields positive outcomes. There is no doubt that in schools with principals who exhibited strong digital leadership, teachers used technology at significantly higher rates. In this sense, the school leader sets an example for all

teachers about the integration or advancement of technology. As a result, having a clear vision serves as a common thread that unites all stakeholders in the digital transition. Students are more engaged when their teachers are more prepared, and this will lead to a positive adoption of digital transformation. Additionally, school leaders need to establish an environment where all instructors may continue to develop if they want technology integration to be successful. Enabling educators to confidently use and integrate technology requires a focus on individualized continuous professional development. Moreover, for technology integration to be successful, school administrators must create a space where all teachers may continue to grow. Prioritizing individualized ongoing professional development is necessary to enable educators to use and integrate technology with confidence. Additionally, promoting technology use raises a number of issues, including privacy and digital conduct, which can be secured by practicing digital literacy and using appropriate online conduct. Also, a strong bond with the community is very important to make everything successful. As leaders, there must be a community engagement that will involve all the stakeholders. With these, they will be informed of the support and participation needed by the school and learners.

Clear Vision

Educational leaders must create a detailed plan for bringing technology into the school. This plan should be aligned with the overall aims of the school. Everyone concerned, including teachers, students, and parents should know why this plan is essential and what advantages it has. In this way, technology can advance teaching and increase educational success for all. (Qasimov, 2025). Furthermore, by inspiring school vision, principals encourage successful technology integration and encourage teachers to use technology in the classroom (Raman, 2019).

Continuous Professional Development

Leaders must support continuous training and professional development for teachers to enable them to utilize technology effectively. This enables an environment where continuous learning and adaptability become a regular aspect of daily life. (Emmanuel, 2025)

Ethical Approach

Leaders have an obligation to ensure that technology is utilized in a just and responsible manner. They must pay attention to important issues. First, they should ensure that individuals' privacy is maintained when dealing with data. Secondly, technology must be made available to all, irrespective of their circumstances. Finally, leaders must ensure that there is no unjust bias in digital tools. By doing these, leaders can lead the responsible utilization of technology. (Hamzah et al., 2021)

Digital Citizenship

Leaders must educate students and employees on how to use computers and the

internet responsibly and safely. They must emphasize cybersecurity, ensuring everyone understands how to keep their personal data secure online. Leaders must also promote good behavior when using technology, ensuring everyone is respectful to others. Leaders must also assist individuals in developing critical thinking skills so they can critically evaluate the validity of information they obtain from the internet. (Sarong, 2024)

Community Engagement

By involving parents, community groups, and decision-makers in technology projects, we have more people behind us. It also ensures that our initiative to incorporate digital tools is sustainable and lasts for years to come. (Zhong, 2016)

2. Teachers' Challenges in Technological Integration

Table 3 highlights the different challenges that teachers encounter when implementing technology into the classroom, including restricted access to resources like digital tools and internet connectivity. Many teachers and students in remote locations struggle to find digital resources that can help them and facilitate an efficient teaching and learning process, particularly in online classes where students must attend sessions and turn in tasks using their devices. This issue results in a digital divide that deprives students of equitable and ongoing educational opportunities. Another major obstacle to teachers' successful use of technology is the lack of ongoing professional development opportunities. For this barrier to be removed, updated training and seminars are required. When educators get generic training and seminars, they are poorly equipped to integrate technology in a meaningful way, which leads to a superficial use of technology instead of a transformative instructional tool that will increase learning effectiveness and engagement. These challenges are interconnected with one another. Teachers might end up so frustrated due to the lack of resources that they become deeply resistant to changes in the classroom, such as the integration of technology. Clearly, a long-standing topic in education and learning is how much teachers embrace digital technology in their instruction. It is impossible to escape digitalization at the present time; future instruction will be entirely dependent on digital tools and platforms (Qureshi et al., 2021). It merely demonstrates that solving a single problem is insufficient; system-based solutions—rather than just short-term ones—are much needed. As a result, the findings of various studies show that teachers are facing these challenges, which serve as barriers to the integration of technology at a time when face-to-face instruction is not the sole method used by different institutions to continue the educational process of the students they teach. It is essential that these concerns be addressed. It will be easier for educators to accept change if they have the necessary tools for the job, feel supported, and possess the necessary skills. It will therefore contribute to a successful digital transformation in the technical environment with a belief that technology serves as a bridge rather than a barrier between the various components of high-quality education.

Limited Access to Resources

In accordance with the different studies, schools face challenges when it comes to integrating technology into the classroom. Issues originating from technology, such as

insufficient access to computers, the internet, and technology education, and others. (Pelila, J. R. O. et al., 2022). Teachers typically have a hard time getting the technology they need, like computers and reliable internet connections. It is even harder in rural areas or where schools do not have money. It creates a "digital divide" that keeps students from getting an equal education. During COVID-19, teachers and students in the Philippines suffered due to the fact that they lacked sufficient tools for online education (Baticulon et al., 2021). Most schools have outdated buildings and equipment, thereby hindering the use of technology (Pelila et al., 2022). There are still issues in the Philippines with a shortage of digital skills and appropriate hardware (Mastul et al., 2023). This can be addressed through policy changes, further funding, and improved facilities (Almacen et al., 2023).

Resistance to Change

Teachers are generally resistant to the use of technology. They might feel uneasy with new technologies, be concerned that it will add to their workload, or doubt its effectiveness in teaching. Based on Vakaliuk et al., 2022, educators have the tendency to consider technology as a distraction rather than a useful resource, hence resorting to outdated approaches instead. Dalinger & Asino, 2021 inform us that educators avoid technology when it appears too complicated, which highlights the need for personalized training initiatives. Anthony (2023) propounds that low self-confidence in applying technology is usually exacerbated by poor leadership support that does not demonstrate its application. In addressing such an issue, one must develop a culture where innovation is supported through mentoring, incentivizing, and displaying evident outcomes of using technology (Sarong, 2023).

Lack of Professional Development

Ineffective training programs render instructors ill-equipped to use technology with purpose. Caena & Redecker (2019) highlight the disparity between generic ICT training and classroom realities, resulting in shallow technology applications. Jadman & Cabigas (2023) reveal that Filipino instructors participated in webinars during the COVID-19 pandemic but missed follow-up resources for retaining the skills. Boholano et al. (2021) promote ongoing hands-on workshops (e.g., on LMS platforms) as a way of filling competency gaps. Sustainable solutions include continuous, context-relevant training consistent with curriculum objectives (Shibing, 2024) and leadership-supported PD initiatives (Hamzah et al., 2021).

3. Teachers Training and Professional Development

The use of technology in the classroom requires more than just having access to digital tools. To ensure that everything is in line with the curriculum, teachers must undergo extensive training. This is an essential part of a successful implementation. To build their confidence, they require a great deal of ongoing mentoring and practical experience from experts that goes beyond the fundamentals of ICT. Workshops that demonstrate and implement the use of digital tools are essential for improving teachers' assessment practices and various engagement strategies. Additionally, incorporating ICT

into the curriculum while providing top-notch teacher preparation supports instruction that is in line with 21st-century learning.

Technical Skills training

Technical skill is a basic barrier, as Raman (2019) and Pelilla et al. (2022) established that teachers may lack skills beyond basic ICT application. Jadman & Cabigas (2023) research promotes practical workshops on tools such as learning management systems (LMS) and AI platforms (Familoni & Onyebuchi, 2024). The LAS (2020) research suggests applying algorithmic tools (e.g., J48 Algorithm) to evaluate and forecast teachers' techno-pedagogical competence to allow targeted skill development.

Professional Development Workshops

Continuous workshops are essential to meet changing technologies. Indalecio (2022) emphasize best practice-sharing learning communities among teachers. Shibing (2024) emphasizes workshops in emerging tools (e.g., augmented reality) to make teaching practice future-proof. The review of the Philippine K-12 system (Almerino et al., 2020) demands workshops based on industry needs, especially in Technical-Vocational Education (TVE) (Barcelona et al., 2023).

Continuous Support

The success of blended learning activities and instructors' positive perspectives toward them are greatly influenced by institutional support during the planning, design, and execution stages (Vergonia & Mombas, 2022). Moreover, continuous support and resources are extremely crucial. According to (Bernardo et al., 2020), teachers remain resilient if they receive ongoing assistance, such as peer coaching, where they assist one another, and help desks for support. In addition, (Mastul et al., 2023), found that a majority of schools in the Philippines do not have required facilities. They requested the government to ensure schools have good internet and provide financial assistance for hardware purchases. Also, (Caluza, et al., 2017) recommended conducting regular feedback sessions to regularly review teachers' progress and modify their training accordingly.

Integration of ICT in Curriculum

To successfully bring Information and Communication Technology (ICT) into education, it's important to include it right in the curriculum design. Kilag et al., (2023); Anthony, (2023); studies suggest making smart policy changes that ensure ICT meets national standards. Valverde-Berrocoso et al., (2022), shows that when teachers receive specific training for their subjects—such as using interactive software for Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM)—students often achieve better results. Programs like the TVET initiatives led by TESDA, referenced by Edralin and Pastrana in 2023, are good examples of how aligning what is taught with industry needs can help bridge skill gaps.

Conclusions

The findings show the role of effective leadership in facilitating an effective integration of technology into educational settings by having a clear vision for all the members of the institution, supporting the continuous development of every teacher being the role model of the institution and having excellent engagement with the members of the community. In spite of that, the teachers still face different challenges in the implementation, such as limited access to resources, resistance to change, and lack of professional development. Good leadership itself is not enough; it must be joined with comprehensive training, which is very important for every teacher to be equipped with appropriate knowledge and skills that will support them in the integration of technology as a roadmap for an effective digital shift in education.

Recommendation

Future studies should look into how leadership interventions and technology integration affect different educational contexts in the Philippines and other developing countries over the long run. This involves investigating localized difficulties and culturally adaptive teaching methods.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers of this study affirm that there are no conflicts of interest, biases and the systematic review is solely focused on analyzing existing studies related to technology integration in educational settings.

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